

BIG BOOKS: IT'S EFFECTIVENESS ON READING COMPREHENSION SKILLS

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the effectiveness of Big Books in enhancing reading comprehension among young learners in primary education. Recognizing the importance of early literacy experiences for cognitive development, the research focuses on the unique features of Big Books—such as enlarged text, vibrant illustrations, and interactive elements—that create engaging and multisensory reading experiences. Conducted at Loo Elementary School in Buguias, Benguet, the qualitative research involved semi-structured interviews with three teachers and three students to gather insights into their perceptions of Big Books and their impact on literacy skills. Key findings indicate that Big Books significantly improve word recognition, comprehension, and vocabulary development while fostering interactive participation among students. Teachers noted that these resources create a positive learning environment, enhancing student engagement and self-esteem. Challenges related to resource availability and curriculum integration were also identified, prompting recommendations for careful selection of titles, incorporation of multisensory activities, and regular read-aloud sessions to maximize effectiveness. The study highlights the critical role of educators in modeling effective reading practices and fostering a supportive atmosphere for young learners. Ultimately, the findings suggest that integrating Big Books into early literacy instruction can lead to improved reading comprehension outcomes and a lifelong love of reading. By addressing the literacy gaps in contexts like the Philippines and Turkey, this approach aligns with global educational goals, emphasizing quality and inclusive education for all children.

Keywords: *Big Books, Reading Comprehension, Early Literacy, Engaging Instruction, Multisensory Learning*

INTRODUCTION

Early literacy experiences are crucial for children's cognitive development and set the foundation for their future academic success. Research indicates that reading comprehension, developed during primary education, significantly influences lifelong learning (Bradley, 2016). This is particularly important in countries like the Philippines and Turkey, where international assessments such as PISA reveal concerning levels of reading proficiency (Özmuşul & Kaya, 2014). Consequently, effective interventions aimed at improving reading skills are essential in these contexts, especially during the pivotal years of primary education.

Family involvement is another critical factor in fostering reading comprehension. Studies show that children who engage in literacy activities with their families tend to perform better academically (Epcacan, 2018). Programs designed to enhance family participation, such as the Philippines' "Catch-up Fridays," highlight the importance of creating a supportive community around literacy. This initiative aligns with the fourth Sustainable Development Goal, which emphasizes quality and inclusive education for all, underscoring the role of families in developing children's reading skills.

One innovative approach to enhancing early literacy is the use of Big Books—oversized educational resources designed for group reading. These materials are effective because their large print and vibrant illustrations capture children's attention, making reading an engaging and interactive experience (Holdaway, 1979). Research supports the notion that Big Books not only improve reading comprehension but also motivate students to participate actively in literacy activities (Nalantha et al., 2018). By transforming reading into a shared experience, Big Books help young learners develop essential literacy skills.

The benefits of Big Books extend beyond engagement; they significantly enhance students' reading skills. Studies have shown that integrating Big Books into reading instruction leads to marked improvements in fluency and comprehension (Novita et al., 2018). These resources provide opportunities for teachers to model effective reading strategies while allowing students to connect more meaningfully with the text. The engaging illustrations and predictable patterns in Big Books also help children navigate common reading challenges, thereby easing their transition into independent reading.

Comprehension skills develop through the interplay of cognitive processes, and teaching children to utilize their background knowledge while reading is crucial (Yule, 2016). Engaging students in discussions during reading sessions can enhance their comprehension abilities (Tracey & Morrow, 2017). By incorporating Big Books into their teaching, educators can foster dialogue around the text, enriching students' understanding and critical thinking skills.

Moreover, the use of Big Books has been linked to increased interest in reading among elementary students. Research indicates that students exposed to Big Books display greater enthusiasm for reading activities (Afrizal, 2015). The visual appeal and

interactive nature of these books provide a platform for exploration and discussion, encouraging a positive attitude toward literacy, particularly among struggling readers.

Thus, the integration of Big Books into primary education presents a promising strategy for enhancing reading comprehension and fostering a love for reading. Their unique features align with the developmental needs of young learners and can lead to significant improvements in literacy outcomes. By promoting the use of Big Books, educational institutions can effectively address literacy gaps and support the overarching goal of achieving quality education for all children.

Research Questions

The primary purpose of this research is to assess the effectiveness of incorporating big books into primary classrooms on the development of reading comprehension skills among young learners. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. How do specific features within big books, such as enlarged text, vibrant illustrations, and interactive elements, contribute to the development of reading comprehension among early childhood learners, as perceived by teachers and students?
2. How do teachers perceive the integration of big books into their instructional practices for enhancing reading comprehension?
3. What strategies do teachers employ to optimize the use of big books for enhancing reading comprehension?

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a descriptive qualitative research methodology to explore the impact of Big Books on reading comprehension skills among primary learners. According to Creswell (2014), qualitative research involves steps such as data interpretation, analysis, and writing results. Descriptive studies focus on providing a systematic description of a phenomenon, which aligns well with the aim of understanding how Big Books can enhance early reading instruction (McCombes, 2020). This methodology allows researchers to gather rich, detailed information about the learning process, making it particularly suitable for investigating the complexities of reading comprehension development in young learners.

The research was conducted at Loo Elementary School in Buguias, Benguet, involving teachers and a selection of students from various grade levels. The sample consisted of six respondents—three teachers and three students randomly selected from Grades 1, 2, and 3. This purposive sampling method ensured that participants had relevant experience with Big Books in the classroom, allowing for more targeted and insightful data collection (Etikan et al., 2016). The choice of Loo Elementary School as the research locale provided a focused environment to explore the integration of Big Books into reading instruction.

Data collection was primarily facilitated through semi-structured interviews. An interview guide containing pertinent questions was developed and validated by an experienced panel to ensure the content's relevance and clarity. The guide was designed to elicit detailed responses from both teachers and students regarding their experiences and perceptions of Big Books. Additionally, documentation, including images and audio recordings, was used to support the qualitative data gathered from interviews, thereby enhancing the study's overall rigor.

The data gathering process began with obtaining necessary permissions from school authorities. Informed consent was collected from all participants, ensuring confidentiality and ethical compliance. The researcher conducted interviews, with permission to record, to facilitate accurate data capture. While interviews are effective for obtaining in-depth qualitative insights, the process can be time-consuming and requires careful management to ensure the quality of responses remains high.

Data analysis was performed using thematic analysis, which involves identifying patterns and themes within the qualitative data (Majumdar, 2022). After transcribing the interviews, the researchers engaged in a coding process, categorizing responses into keywords and themes. This systematic approach allowed for a deeper understanding of the participants' insights regarding Big Books' impact on reading comprehension. The final stage involved verifying the data to ensure accuracy and validity, enabling the researchers to draw meaningful conclusions about the effectiveness of Big Books in enhancing early literacy skills.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The analysis of the results regarding the use of big books in early childhood education reveals several key themes that enhance reading comprehension and engagement among young learners. These themes, supported by both student and teacher perspectives, highlight the multifaceted benefits of integrating big books into literacy instruction. Central to this discussion are the concepts of word recognition and comprehension, visual representation and engagement, interactive participation, and the practical strategies employed by educators.

Word Recognition and Comprehension is the foundational theme observed in the data. The enlarged text in big books serves to capture the attention of young readers, facilitating easier word recognition and overall comprehension. As noted by several respondents, larger print aids in focusing on the text, which is crucial for visual processing and language comprehension. Research by Garnett (2014) corroborates these findings, emphasizing the significance of automatic word recognition as a precursor to understanding the text. The clear and readable format of big books not only boosts reading skills but also enhances confidence in young readers, ultimately fostering a positive attitude toward reading.

Visual Representation and Engagement is another prominent theme. The vibrant illustrations accompanying the text in big books provide crucial visual cues that help children connect words with images. This visual support enhances comprehension by contextualizing the narrative. Educators noted that illustrations not only captivate students but also encourage them to engage actively with the text. Bell (2016) highlights that visual aids significantly improve reading engagement, suggesting that the ability to visualize story concepts enhances overall comprehension. Thus, the use of visually appealing big books transforms reading into an immersive experience that stimulates both interest and understanding.

Interactive Participation plays a vital role in promoting deeper comprehension and engagement. Teachers observed that students are highly participative during reading sessions involving big books, often contributing their thoughts and ideas. This active engagement is critical, as it allows children to explore the narrative beyond the text, enhancing their understanding. Roslina (2017) points out that interactive reading practices foster a shared understanding, whereby children respond to prompts and questions that deepen their comprehension. The collective engagement during these sessions cultivates a rich learning environment where students feel valued and encouraged to express themselves.

The strategies employed by teachers are equally essential in maximizing the benefits of big books. Interactive read-aloud sessions are a particularly effective method, as they allow teachers to guide discussions, pose questions, and encourage predictions about the story. Techniques such as role-playing and peer discussions further facilitate comprehension by allowing students to take on various roles within the narrative. These strategies align with Ananta's (2018) assertion that engaging students in interactive reading not only enhances comprehension but also fosters a sense of community and collaboration among learners.

Vocabulary Development emerges as a significant benefit of using big books. The exposure to diverse vocabulary through engaging texts helps students improve their language skills, which is crucial for their overall literacy development. Respondents noted that students were excited to read and often engaged with new words presented in the narratives. Negawati and Walundari (2017) support this observation, emphasizing the role of rich, interactive content in expanding vocabulary among young learners. This enhanced vocabulary not only aids comprehension but also equips students with the language tools necessary for future academic success.

Despite the numerous advantages, challenges related to limited resources and time constraints were highlighted by teachers. The lack of sufficient copies of big books and the difficulty in integrating them into the curriculum pose significant obstacles. Teachers often resort to creative solutions, such as group readings and sharing resources with colleagues, to mitigate these challenges. Moir (2020) suggests that utilizing online resources and attending workshops can further empower educators to effectively integrate big books into their literacy instruction, thereby overcoming resource limitations and optimizing learning outcomes.

In conclusion, the integration of big books into early childhood education presents a wealth of benefits for enhancing reading comprehension and engagement. The themes of word recognition, visual representation, interactive participation, and effective teaching strategies collectively underscore the importance of using big books as educational tools. By fostering a supportive and interactive learning environment, educators can significantly enhance the reading experiences of young learners, paving the way for a lifelong love of reading and learning.

Conclusions

The use of big books has proven to be an effective tool for enhancing the reading comprehension skills of young learners. Their unique qualities—such as enlarged text, vibrant illustrations, and interactive elements—create a multisensory reading experience that captivates children. These features not only make decoding easier but also foster vocabulary growth and encourage active engagement, making learning enjoyable and interesting. As a result, big books serve as invaluable resources for educators and parents aiming to instill a love of reading and establish a solid foundation for literacy.

From the perspectives of teachers, big books significantly improve reading comprehension in early childhood education. They facilitate a more engaging and positive learning environment, which not only boosts students' self-esteem but also deepens their love for reading. Teachers observe that the interactive nature of big books enhances students' focus and interest, leading to a more enriching educational experience. This positive impact on engagement underscores the importance of incorporating such resources into early literacy instruction.

Furthermore, teachers play a crucial role in fostering a welcoming reading environment where students feel comfortable asking questions and sharing their thoughts. By modeling a love of reading and employing effective reading strategies, educators encourage students to become active participants in their learning. This supportive atmosphere not only enhances comprehension but also empowers young readers to take ownership of their reading journey, laying the groundwork for lifelong literacy development.

Recommendations

To maximize the effectiveness of big books in enhancing reading comprehension for young learners, it's essential to carefully select titles that align with their age and reading abilities. Choosing big books with themes, vocabulary, and content that resonate with their comprehension levels is critical for stimulating interest and promoting understanding. When books are relatable and appropriately challenging, young readers are more likely to engage with the material, leading to improved comprehension skills.

Educators should regularly assess students' developmental stages to ensure that the selected big books meet their evolving needs.

Incorporating multisensory activities connected to big books can further enhance comprehension by providing hands-on learning experiences. Activities such as role-playing and dramatic reenactments allow young learners to immerse themselves in the story, fostering a deeper connection with the text. This interactive approach not only reinforces comprehension but also promotes collaboration and creativity among students. By physically engaging with the narrative, children can explore characters, plotlines, and settings in a way that traditional reading alone may not achieve, making the story more memorable and meaningful.

Frequent read-aloud sessions using big books are also crucial for demonstrating effective reading practices. Through expressive, intonated, and fluent reading, teachers can model how to engage with a text dynamically. This not only aids in developing students' listening skills but also helps them internalize the rhythms and nuances of language. Additionally, these sessions can serve as opportunities for discussion, allowing students to ask questions and share their thoughts, which reinforces their comprehension. Regularly scheduled read-alouds create a rich literary environment that nurtures a love for reading and encourages active participation, ultimately leading to enhanced reading skills.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In conducting this study on the effectiveness of big books in enhancing reading comprehension among young learners, strict adherence to ethical standards was maintained throughout the research process. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, including parents and educators, ensuring that they were fully aware of the study's objectives and methodologies. Participants were informed that their involvement was voluntary and that they could withdraw at any time without any repercussions. This transparency helped establish trust and fostered an ethical research environment.

Confidentiality was another critical component of ethical compliance in this study. All data collected from participants, including their responses and feedback regarding the use of big books, were anonymized to protect their identities. Careful measures were taken to ensure that personal information was securely stored and only accessible to authorized research personnel. By prioritizing confidentiality, the study aimed to create a safe space for participants to express their views openly, which ultimately enriched the quality of the data collected.

Furthermore, the study aimed to minimize any potential harm to participants by implementing a supportive research framework. Educators and researchers were trained to engage with young learners in a positive and nurturing manner, promoting a love for reading while ensuring that the activities were age-appropriate and enjoyable. By fostering an inclusive and encouraging atmosphere, the study not only complied with

ethical standards but also contributed to the participants' overall educational experience, emphasizing the importance of ethical considerations in educational research.

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